
RIVER BENUE AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF TRADE AND INTERGROUP RELATIONS IN THE BENUE VALLEY SINCE THE PRECOLONIAL PERIOD

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Abstract: *Water bodies have played significant roles in human history and culture, hence, their influence on societies cannot be ignored. This is also the case with the River Benue which takes its source from Northern Cameroon and flows over 1,400 Km westward to meet the River Niger as one its largest tributaries. It is true that rivers can act as natural obstacles or even boundaries in some cases, but many societies have mastered the art of harnessing water resources and, since the colonial period, the River Benue has been utilised by the peoples of the Benue Valley including those along its banks and beyond for various purposes including agriculture, fishing, trade, exploration, raids, communication, transportation and cultural transmission. The depth and breadth of the River permitted all year - round travelling for different groups including the early European explorers and missionaries. This paper therefore examines the role played by the River Benue in the development of trade and intergroup relations in the Benue Valley beginning from the precolonial period up to the postcolonial period. The paper relied on the analysis of extant literature and oral interviews as well as archival materials and the methodology is essentially historical. The paper was conceived against the backdrop that an understanding of the dynamics of trade and intergroup relations in the Benue Valley with the River Benue as a medium is important in properly harnessing and managing the resources of the area given the heterogeneous and diverse cultures present in the area.*

Keywords: *River Benue, Trade and Commerce, Intergroup Relations, Benue Valley History and Waterways and Cultural Interaction.*

Introduction

Trade constitutes an important component of human interaction more so as it evens out the disparities that exist in terms of resource endowment between individuals and groups. Through trade, what an individual or societies has is given out in exchange for what is desired. There is also a nexus between trade and intergroup relations as there is the need for interaction for trade to occur. In the past, these interactions necessarily had to be physical interaction for trade to occur even if the use of

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intermediaries was adopted. The history of Nigerian peoples is replete with records of interactions across land, desert, rivers, seas and oceans despite the fact that transport technology was not as sophisticated as it is today. The peoples of the Nigeria area were able to harness the resources around them to the extent that they could interact with other groups well beyond their regions as demonstrated through the Trans-Saharan Trade in the North as well as the Trans-Atlantic Slave and Legitimate trades.

It is worthy to note that humans are gregarious and depend on each other for survival. This is also the case with human groups and communities which have had to depend on other communities to satisfy certain wants and needs irrespective of their level of development. Since societies are hardly self-sufficient or independent, there is always the need to relate or depend on other societies leading to inter-group relations. Sometimes, inter-group relations predates trade or exchange between communities as it is the relations established that paves way for the exchange of trading in goods and services. Like modern societies, precolonial societies too were able to realise the importance of intergroup relations. For instance, fishing communities were able to understand that they needed to relate with communities that were involved in crop farming in order to obtain tubers grains and other food crops while the farming community also realised that they needed to relate with the fishing community to meet their demand for fish.

The Benue Valley is home to a plethora of ethnic groups with varying degrees of endowment. The region is highly populated by groups which include the Tiv, Idoma, Jukun and many other groups. This large population is as a result of many factors including the rich alluvial soil deposits of the area which support the production of a wide range of crops such as grains and tubers. Despite these endowments, the peoples of the Valley like other human groups had to relate with other groups such as the groups in the hinterlands, the savannah peoples as well as groups within the Benue Valley. These relations were borne out of the need to survive and the relations bordered on trade, alliances, cultural exchanges and even conflict. This is because, wherever, there is interaction among groups, conflict becomes inevitable. The penetration of the area by Europeans was to completely change the dynamics of interaction more so as the River facilitated European activities in the region.

This paper therefore examines how the River Benue was leveraged upon as medium of transportation which facilitated trade and intergroup relations between the peoples of the Benue Valley. There is no doubt that the river served as a form of barricade in some instances by limiting interaction and communication between the hinterland and the Savannah area of the entity now referred to as Nigeria. However, the history of human society and development revolves around the mastery of the environment and especially the ability to surmount challenges. The River Benue may have served as an obstacle but is also served as a buffer in certain circumstances; this is also not forgetting the significant use it was put to by the peoples of the Benue Valley who were able to harness the potential

of the River as a means of transportation even before contact with Europe was established. The scope of this paper therefore covers the pre-colonial, colonial and post-colonial period.

Conceptual Clarification

Inter-Group Relations

Nwabueze in his sociological view of inter-group relations argues that inter-group relations is the totality of human relations and the techniques as well as mechanisms for managing same. He posits that:

The simple or complex, conflicting or accommodating, co-operating, consensus, peaceful or acrimonious, intense, dense or indifferent way that a group is connected or associated with another in the course of their interaction with each other. Inter-group relations as a study focuses essentially on the series of methods, strategies or approaches to the understanding of separate group dynamics, of diffusing tension between different groups and creating or building bridges across potential or actual conflict relationships or directly promoting harmony. It may also be repackage curriculum for conflict management and containment based on scientific understanding of group characteristics and a more accurate capacity to predict the patterns of prejudices, preferences, and sentiments among and between groups in interaction with one another.

The import of this definition lies in the fact that apart from its comprehensiveness, it has been able to capture the important components of inter-group relations. First, that every interaction can either be harmonious or conflicting and that conflict can be avoided through the understanding of group's dynamics or ways of life, and so inter-group relation can be useful for conflict management. Again it agrees with the fact that inter-group relation is an integral part of human existence.

Okpeh also agrees that inter-group relations is an integral part of human existence when by submitting that inter-group relations is multidimensional in nature and originates from contacts and interactions between different groups as they struggle to re-create their material well-being. Afolabi and Aderonke, also agree with Okpeh by noting that inter-group relations refers to the interaction between the various ethnics groups that make up Nigeria. According to Afolabi and Aderonke, interactions within the framework of inter-group relations could be in various forms-political, economic, military and social. This argument implies that these interactions could be positive interactions or negative interactions. They are positive when the interacting groups live in relative harmony and benefit from each other and negative when the groups are exposed to rivalry and unhealthy competition, resulting in tensions, bitterness and hostilities.

According to Afigbo;

Inter-group relations presupposes contact and interaction between groups each of which has an identity, to make some inputs into the relationships, in short, each of which has some scope and area of autonomous action.

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The interesting issues raised in this definition are that, inter-group relations entails contact and interaction between groups. This implies that inter-group relations refers to the interaction between groups that are otherwise distinct for the purpose of achieving individual or collective objective that are dependent on these interactions which may be either harmonious or in the form of conflict.

An Overview of the Benue Valley

The term “Benue Valley” is a geographical expression often used to describe the vast lowland surrounding the River Benue. The area stretches from the confluence of the Benue and the Niger Rivers, and extends for more than 800 kilometers covering all, or parts of six states of Nigeria. The Valley occupies 82,298 km² (31,775 mi²) within the area marked by 6° 30' E and 11° 00' E and 6° 15' N and 9° 30' N. Its boundaries to the west are the Niger and Okwa Rivers, to the north, a dissected zone separates it from the higher Jemaa platform, Jos Plateau and Gongola Plains: to the east the boundary is Nigeria's North East referred to as Sardauna Province present day Adamawa State. The southern boundary is marked by the borders of the hitherto East Central State and South East State, except in the extreme south-east where the boundary follows the Katsina Ala watershed. It is important to mention here that the River Benue itself forms the main axis of the area and falls from 90 m (300 ft) in the east to 45 m (150 ft) at its confluence with the Niger.

Extensive plains slope irregularly on either side of the River Benue towards the River from a height of about 150 m (500 ft). To the north of the Benue these plains rise gradually to the foot of the dissected zone marking the northern boundary of the Benue Valley, reaching a height of 600 m (2,000 ft) in the north-east, South of the Benue River, to the south and east of Katsina Ala town the plains rise gently to the foot of an escarpment which rises from 300 m (1,000 ft) to over 1,500 m (5,000 ft) on the Obudu Plateau. South of Makurdi lies an area of plains rising to almost 210 m (700 ft). To the west of Otukpo the major relief feature is the Ankpa Plateau consisting of plains over 300 m (1,000 ft). It is marked on the north and east "by a strongly dissected zone and an escarpment and the Plateau itself is cut into "by steeply incised streams, the headwaters of the Anambra River and its tributaries.

Much of the Benue Valley is drained by the Benue River and its tributaries but in the south west, the Anambra River system drains to the Niger, whilst the Ogwa and Konshisha Rivers drain southwards to the Cross River. The dominant climate of this area is the Tropical Guinea Savannah. The Guinea Belt covers the limits of the tropical rainforest climate, and extends to Central Nigeria where it forms a boundary with the Sudan savanna, exhibiting a clearly defined single peak rainy season and a dry season. The 1951-2009 average minimum, mean and maximum temperature values are 22.3±2.5 °C, 27.8±1.8 °C and 33.3±2.6 °C, respectively while the mean relative humidity for same period is 69.8±14.2%. The area has an annual rainfall which ranges from 1500mm – 2000mm while the mean annual rainfall is about 1200 mm. Normally, the rainy season lasts from April to October, while the dry season lasts from November to March. The ecological underlain is primarily sedimentary, with micaceous and feldspathic sandstone in some portions of the area, and shale in some low-lying. Main

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soil types are hydromorphic soils that developed on alluvium sediments along River Benue coastline, as well as red ferasols away from the coastline.

The states covered by the Benue Valley presently include Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Plateau, southern Kaduna and southern Bauchi. It extends from Taraba State and stretched southwards to the confluence of the Rivers Niger and Benue in Kogi State. As a result of the influence of good drainage, rich soil and grassland that makes cultivation relatively easier than what obtains in the rainforest belt, the region has the highest concentration of highly complex multi-ethnic, multi-lingual and multi-cultural society. According to Varvar:

The physical environment of the Benue Valley area posed very little problems to human habitation and exploitation, and the near absence of mountain ranges and hills allowed for relatively easy movement and made it possible for the people to effectively take control and establish settlement over the extensive area.

The submission by Varvar therefore explains why the Benue Valley is home to many of the minority groups in Nigeria such as, Tiv, Idoma, Jukun, Nupe, Birom, Igbira, Igala, Chamba, Alago, Bassa, Angas, Igede, Eggon, Kuteb, Nyifon among several others. The concentration of people of diverse cultural background in the area has been explained to be as a result of the favourable geographical conditions which naturally encouraged people from all nook and crannies of the country to migrate and settle in the area since the pre-colonial period. Over 60% of the indigenous people are small-scale or indigenous farmers, and many of the farmers are also fishermen, depending on their locations. The population density as at 2016 was estimated at 405,000 and projected to rise to about 600,000 by 2021,

The ethnic groups in the Benue Valley are classified as minorities when compared to the major groups in Nigeria Hausa\ - Fulani, Igbo and Yoruba. Christianity and Islam are the two major religions found in the area. Some people in the area are African Traditional worshipers. Most of the ethnic groups in the Valley are found in more than one state. For instance, the Tiv are not only in Benue State, which is regarded as their geographical compact, but are also found in great numbers in Nasarawa, Taraba and Plateau States. The Jukun are not only in Taraba State, but are also found in Benue and Nasarawa states. The Bassa are in Nasarawa and Kogi States. The Egbura (Ebira) are also in Kogi and Nasarawa States. The Idoma are found in both Benue and Nasarawa States.

Pre – Colonial Trade and Intergroup Relations in the Valley

There are indications that intergroup relations existed in the Benue Valley during the pre-colonial period even as these relations were not always peaceful. For instance, the Jukun relied on the River Benue to establish trading relations with the Igala and Nupe. Overland, the Tiv used to produce yams and grains in exchange for fish from the Jukun. The grains obtained from the Tiv were used by the Jukun in their brewing industries. The Alago who left Kwararafa and Idah in the 17th century and settled at Keana also had harmonious relations with the Tiv. The Tiv used to exchange their food

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products with the Alago who were specialized and pre-occupied with the production of salt. There was also the existence of trade between the groups in the Benue Valley with their neighbours. Human porters made use of local roads or bush-paths that linked neighbouring villages, city states and even kingdoms and empires over land except in areas farther north where beasts like camels, donkeys and horses were used. Prominent market centres developed like Idah, Otukpo, Onyagede, Makurdi, Lafia, among others. This led to specialization in the art of trading but also led to the organization of trade in the Benue Valley as trade was formally organized and distribution of goods and services properly perfected in the region. Apart from the development of markets, the people of the Benue Valley became specialized in the art of trading especially among the groups that served as middle-men between the groups in the Benue Valley and the traders that came from other areas. According to Iyo, the Tiv, clearly emerged as middle men and guides in the substantial salt trade and probably controlled the free passages on the caravan trade routes. The Igala too acted as middle men in the trading transaction between the Idoma and the Igbo and Hausa as well as Benin and Old Oyo and part of this trade involved crossing or travelling along the River Benue to as far as the confluence of the River Niger.

Apart from the trade that was carried out among the groups in the Benue Valley, these groups also embarked on trade relations with the Hausa and upper Cross River groups during the pre-colonial period. The Hausa provided iron tools, indigo, European clothes, brass pans, shea butter and honey in exchange for Tiv items which were principally agricultural surpluses like yams and grains. According to Ochefu:

The Tiv had been able to exploit trading relations with the Borno Empire, the Hausa States...Yola and Bekwara in the Upper Cross River Valley, the bulk of Tiv external trade revolved around the exchange of clothes, salt, dried fish, ivory, cattle and agricultural surpluses especially yams and grain.

The Igala also traded with the Hausa and Igbo. They traded with the Igbo, Hausa, Benin and old Oyo and as middle men, they distributed the clothes, dyes and other European goods brought by the Igbo to the Idoma in exchange for Idoma goods like tobacco, coral beads, slaves and horses which were in high demand in Igboland. Trade was also carried out between the Jukun, the Hausa, Igbo and groups in the Upper Cross River Basin. The Jukun provided slaves, palm produce and yams as well as salt for the people of Old Calabar who brought fish and salt for exchange. There was also trade relations between the Idoma and the Igbo also within this time frame. According to Ochefu and Okpeh, Igbo market and salt producing centre of Uburu was particularly popular among the Idoma. Likewise the Idoma markets of Onyagede, Okpiko, Otukpo and Ochobo were popular among the Igbo.

Apart from trade, intermarriages were a factor for inter-group relations during the period. Intermarriages were quite strategic in inter-group relations because they harmonize relations between groups and made them see each other as a family. The groups served as protectors of each other. According to Afigbo, some married into prominent families along trade routes to ensure their

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safety, extend their business contacts and secure accommodation facilities. Afigbo Also pointed out that an Igala by name Amedu Oji married Oyeri Onyishi from Nsukka so that he would not only facilitate his good relationship with the group in Nsukka but also protect his trade hence both became one family. These cordial interactions even led to cultural transmission as some groups even adopted names from outside groups. Afigbo also cited that personal names on either side of the border in which many Idoma people bear Igbo names as well as the fact in Idoma the markets days bear the same names as in Igboland, are all suggestive of a deep cultural interactions.

The Jukun and the Tiv for instance, had a cordial relationship when they met in the Benue Valley during the 18th Century. According to Tseror, there was a cordial and symbiotic relationship between the Tiv and the Jukun such that, the Aku Uka Zikenju appointed a Tiv man to a Jukun office as early as the 1840s. It is also argued that the Tiv also paid the Jukun back by assisting them in their numerous wars against the Fulani and the Hausa. There are also indications that, trade and exchange occurred between the two groups and that the Tiv learnt the art of salt production from the Jukun. The Jukun thus exchanged their salt, fish and local beer with the Tiv agricultural products like yams and grains. Other dimensions of Tiv-Jukun inter-group relations were in religious matters and inter marriages. Marriage naturally is a principal instrument for the perfection of harmonious relationship among groups. It is worth nothing here that, not that the relationship between the Jukun and the Tiv at any point had acrimony. There were periods when notable cases of wars sprang out among the groups as was witnessed in 1870s, the fact was that such conflicts were quickly resolved. The cause of such wars was the fear by the Jukun of growing Tiv population and Tiv expansionism and fear of domination.

Some Tiv were found among the Alago army as mercenaries in what can be described as a form of military alliance. The Alago recruited the Tiv in large numbers to fight their enemy, the Agwatashi who posed a challenge for the Alago. The Tiv were also recruited to work on Alago farms while the Alago embarked on salt production. The effective use of poisoned arrows for killing by the Tiv was of importance to the Alago who in turn aligned with the Tiv when the Tiv were confronted by the Hausa. The Tiv therefore provided the security for the Alago. According to Tseror, in as much as this relationship was cordial, the Tiv never engaged in intermarriages with the Alago because the Alago women had no strength of working on the farm. As time went on, the relationship started witnessing some changes as there was tension and war over land acquisition and about the numerical strength of the Tiv people in Alago land.

The Jukun/Chamba-Kuteb had long indulged in intermarriages and religious integration. It was suggested that, the Jukun and Kuteb interacted cordially with each other and even exchanged religious and cultic artifacts, names and also intermarried. Despite this long period of relationship, their relationship was not that cordial. This was as a result of divergent interest and fear of domination among them. The arrival of Chamba in Takum was the reason for this. The Jukun after

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losing their home in Cameroon from where they migrated had two options, either survival or extinction. Thus for them to survive, they had to embark on peaceful negotiation with stronger groups and violent assault on the weaker ones. This made the relationship between the Jukun/Chamba-Kuteb very excruciating as all these groups were laying claims to Takum – a place they had all migrated to. It is Important to note that trade and wars were the most dominant aspects of inter-group relations in the Benue Valley during the pre-colonial period and the use of intermediaries meant minimal use of the River Benue. Much of the interaction involving the River Benue took place at crossings until the arrival of the Europeans.

Trade and Intergroup Relations along the River Benue during the Colonial and Post-Colonial Period

The Industrial Revolution in Europe was to have profound effects on the outside world including the Benue Valley where the River Benue was to become an important route in facilitating the penetration of areas far removed from Nigeria's coastal region. The quest for trading areas and sources of raw materials particularly fuelled explorations to areas like Africa. Pertaining the Nigeria area for instance, the exploration of Mungo Park in 1794 paved way for the further explorations of Richard and John Lander and the eventual "discovery" that the Benue flows into the Niger. This would later pave way for Eduard Robert Flegel to reach the source of the River Benue near Ngaundere (in present day Cameroon) between 1882 and 1884.

Before Flegel's discovery, expeditions were carried out by Macgregor Laird, in 1832. It failed but it also revealed the economic potentials of these areas. There was another disastrous expedition in 1841 with the loss of many lives. The interest on the Benue waned but in 1851 William Balfour Baikie was able to sail up to 400 miles up the Benue with British sponsorship. This feat opened up the rivers Benue and Katsina Ala where trading ports and stations were set up at Abinsi, Ibi, and Katsina-Ala by European trading firms. The British alone had numerous companies. The most prominent of these were the West African Company of Manchester, which had links with the Church Missionary Society (CMS) through the Crowder family; Alexander Miller and Brothers of Glasgow; Holland Jacques of London; and James Pinnock of Liverpool. In 1867 a British consulate was established at Lokoja by W. B. Baikie the successor of MacGregor Laird whose idea it was for the Consulate to be established who had died in 1861. By 1870 the West African Company of Manchester started buying ivory at Ibi and Gbamasha. In 1875, Holland Jacques of London ran into financial difficulties and it was acquired by a former army engineer Sir George Taubman Goldie who reconstituted Holland Jacques as the Central African Trading Company in 1876. Sir George Taubman Goldie visited the Niger in 1877 and realized the advantages that would accrue from the amalgamation of the British firms trading on the river then. He persuaded the firms to combine. The United African Company (U.A.C) was thus formed from the amalgamation of these companies in 1879, and in 1881 its name was changed to the National African Company (N.A.C.). This name too would later be changed to Royal Niger Company (RNC)

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which received a charter from the British government to trade and administer the area of around the Niger in 1886.

The RNC embarked upon the purchase of goods which were chiefly agricultural produce. The most important items of trade were ivory and shea butter. The British firms had to compete with the French-led by de Senelle, an agent of the Camaigned de l'Afrique Equatorial, who started purchasing ivory, shea butter, and palm oil from Ibi, Lokoja, and Ega. The large vessels could not come that deep into the hinterland and had to stop at Burutu while boats, barges and small ferries transported produce from hinterlands along the Benue River to Burutu where the goods were loaded unto the large steamers or vessels. The commonest operating unit was one power craft with two barges towed alongside. Since none of the big steamers or ocean going vessels could come inland in the season of low water level, the process of transportation required a tug or vessels of suitable draught pulling some barges up and down the river. The number of barges pulled by each tug or vessel depended upon the installed capacity of its engine. The journey from Burutu to Garua on the River Benue in Cameroun Republic, over a thousand kilometres away took on the average seventeen days, while returning with the current the distance could be completed in eleven days.

There are indications that despite the fact that the River Benue was not navigable throughout the year, during the colonial period, this was the period when it was utilised most for trade owing to the volume of goods that was transported on the River on a daily basis, sometimes goods that could not be transported during the dry season were stored until the waters were deep enough to permit the passage of barges. Precolonial trade along the River Benue significantly affected intergroup relations especially with the influx of Igbo and Hausa traders who served as buying agents for the European firms which were responsible for the purchase of agricultural produce. Significant decline was however witnessed during the post-colonial period especially with the development of land transportation which meant that more goods were moved by road while fewer goods were moved through the River. The situation is further exacerbated by siltation process that had made the River bed quite shallow and lost the depth needed for the transportation of goods and services by even small ships and barges.

Conclusion

It has been demonstrated in this paper that the River Benue was very important in nurturing and sustaining trade and intergroup relations between the peoples of the Benue Valley especially during the colonial period. The river introduced specialization as expert canoe and boat men emerged who transported and ferried traders along the rivers in large canoes, bringing with them commodities and merchandise from the hinterland, and taking home products from inhabitants of the banks of these rivers. With the arrival of the Europeans, time, large trading centres such as John Holt emerged which served meeting places of traders and their goods as well as melting points of cultures. Ideas were crossed leading greater understanding among the peoples of the region. It was as a result of the

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River Benue too that Christian missionary activities were able to penetrate the Benue Valley when they did. The paper however indicates that there was a decline in the traffic level along the River Benue arising mainly from the development of road infrastructure and the construction of bridges across the River as well as siltation of the river bed which has made navigation difficult in many portions of the River.

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Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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